

An investigation into the effects of wildfires on the quality, spatial and temporal distribution of Volunteered Geographic Information

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Summary

This paper investigates the effects of the 2020 California wildfires on Volunteer Geographical Information (VGI). Previous research on VGI has frequently focused on its quality and spatial and temporal variability. This study implements a series of statistical analysis, including spatial autocorrelational and fuzzy clustering, to identify any spatial temporal changes in cases studies both involving and not involving wildfire, to investigate to what extent changes might be a result of wildfires. The analysis shows similar spatial temporal changes of the VGI in both the wildfire and non-wildfire sites, concluding that wildfires do not directly impact VGI.

KEYWORDS: Volunteered Geographic Information, OpenStreetMap, iNaturalist, Wildfires

1. Introduction

Volunteer Geographical Information (VGI) has become a popular topic in Geographic Information Science due to the success of platforms like OpenStreetMap (OSM) [‡] and the rise of user generated content created from social media. Traditionally the focus of VGI literature is on the quality concerns, largely focused on reviewing the data to be used for academic analysis (Barren *et al.*, 2014). Other studies look at making VGI compliant with the guidelines which major spatial data organisations must follow (Fonte *et al.*, 2017). Recently there has been a rise of studies looking at the uneven coverage of VGI (Lorini *et al.*, 2020) and the strengths VGI data can have in disaster management (Ahmouda *et al.*, 2018). This study will take a different look and investigate potential external factors that could influence the spatial and temporal distribution of VGI data with a focus on wildfires. Ahmouda *et al.*, (2018) highlights there is a rise in VGI data following a natural disaster and in 2020 California experienced 9,917 wildfires alone. Combined with the large amount of public available data provided by US state offices, this made it a desirable site of interest for this study.

2. Methodology

The study aimed at creating a reproducible analysis using R, that would allow for data collection, tidying and analysis be completed. This was to ensure that the analysis could be reproduced, whether using the same information or different case studies, VGI platforms or analytical methods.

2.1. Case Study Sites

A series of case studies within the state of California were selected, where a wildfire occurred and the surrounding area to provide a wildfire and non-wildfire comparison. The identification of areas in a 10km buffer from the wildfires was considered for the non-wildfire locations.

The four wildfires used were chosen as the largest wildfires that affected an urban region, a rural region, a region with both and a region with neither urban nor rural characteristics. The urban regions were identified using the California State Geoportal's Adjusted Urban Area data[§] and the rural regions were

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‡ <https://www.openstreetmap.org>

§ https://gis.data.ca.gov/datasets/51e54198fb68443cb0d73390ec46f364_0/explore?location=37.082412%2C-119.393250%2C6.85

identified using the California Protected Area Database^{**}. The use of these four case studies was to remove any potential bias of VGI data being largely focused in urban areas (Lorini *et al.*, 2020).

2.2. Temporal Selection

The wildfire data used contained key metadata including the start and end date of each wildfire, allowing for the identification of the month the wildfire occurred. The three time slots were used to allow for temporal analysis: pre-wildfire, wildfire, and post-wildfire.

2.3. Data Collection

VGI contains large amounts of data making accessing data using traditional methods time consuming from large file downloads and manual data filtering. The use of a programming language like R used in this study ensured that the data can be obtained through an Application Programming Interface (API). The two main VGI platforms used were OSM and iNaturalist^{††}. OSM was used as it is the most well known and completed VGI platform, whereas iNaturalist has a focus on fauna and flora distribution which would have been impacted following a wildfire. The OSM full history data was required for this study meaning the ohsome API^{‡‡} created by the Heidelberg Institute for Geoinformation Technology was used (Klonner *et al.*, 2019). The rinat^{§§} R library for iNaturalist contains an API making it the preferred method for data collection. The collected information included metadata like usernames which were removed to only include the information relevant for the study illustrated in **Table 1**.

Table 1 Data used from API results

Open Street Map API data	iNaturalist API data
osmId	id
version	datetime
validFrom	created_at
validTo	num_identification_agreements
Feature Classes	num_identification_disagreements
	quality_grade
	positional_accuracy
	iconic_taxon_name

2.4. Analytical Methods

The quality measures outlined in **Table 2** were calculated, based on measures of VGI data quality proposed in previous research (Barren *et al.*, 2014). The quality measures were then used as the basis for spatial analysis through spatial autocorrelation and fuzzy c-means clustering.

Spatial Autocorrelation was used to help identify any spatial trends between the different quality methods. This would allow for independent comparisons between each quality check across all timeframes and case study sites. The Local Moran I score was used for spatial autocorrelation and Getis Ord Gi was used for hotspot analysis.

Fuzzy clustering was used as it identifies any spatial patterns that would be present where data points were assigned to more than a singular cluster. The geomeans library in R was used to conduct a Spatial Generalized Fuzzy C-Means cluster analysis (Gelb and Appericio, 2021). This approach allows for the creation of fuzzy clustering maps and an overall test on the stability of each cluster. The test on cluster stability will help in the analysis by identifying the overall confidence of each cluster and therefore knowing how much confidence to put into the outputted result.

^{**} https://gis.data.ca.gov/datasets/6b4a47259383432990de2b858e07c988_2/explore

^{††} <https://www.inaturalist.org>

^{‡‡} <https://docs.ohsome.org/ohsome-api/v1/>

^{§§} <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/rinat/rinat.pdf>

Table 2 Quality Check calculations

Quality Check	Control	OpenStreetMap Calculation	iNaturalist Calculation
Spatial Accuracy		Mean osmId and version that did not change in later months	Mean positional_accuracy
Feature Level Accuracy		Mean version number	Mean Agreement score = num_identification_agreements - num_identification_disagreements
Temporal Accuracy		Mean DateDiff = validTo - validFrom	Mean DateDiff = created_at - datetime
Completeness		Mean number of N/A Values	Mean quality_grade at Research level
Feature Count		Mean of feature classes	Mean of iconic_taxon_name

3. Results

Figure 1 shows an example of spatial autocorrelation results of the iNaturalist both urban and rural wildfire case study site. Each cluster represents sites of recorded information and the different colour hue showing the average agreement scores for the cluster. The pre-wildfire timeframe shows a range of clusters of recorded data with a range of agreement score values. A clear decline in both the number of cluster sites and value range is seen in the wildfire and post-wildfire timeframes, with the post-wildfire seeing some rise in clustering sites. No clear conclusion can be made from this site as seen in **Figure 1** the non-wildfire surrounding site has a similar pattern of changes seen in the wildfire site.

iNaturalist Spatial Autocorrelation results for the Agreement Score of the Both case study site

Figure 1 Spatial Autocorrelation result of the iNaturalist Both Urban and Rural Wildfire (left) and Non-Wildfire (right) case study site for Agreement Score.

Figure 2 shows an example of the final clusters from the fuzzy clustering of the OSM wildfire and non-wildfire neither urban and rural site. Both contain only one clear cluster and have a decline in spatial distribution between the pre-wildfire and wildfire timeframes. The non-wildfire post-wildfire timeframe sees an increase in spatial distribution which is not present in the wildfire site. However, **Figure 3** shows the cluster stability and for cluster 3 in the wildfire site and 1 in the non-wildfire site have an overall low confidence score. Meaning there is low confidence in the result for this site and would need to be compared to patterns seen in other sites before an overall conclusion can be made.

Figure 2 Final clustering results of the OpenStreetMap Neither wildfire (left) and non-wildfire (right) sites

Figure 3 Cluster stability of the OpenStreetMap Neither wildfire (left) and non-wildfire (right) sites

4. Discussion and conclusions

The results demonstrate clear temporal changes but those seem not to be linked to wildfires, as the non-wildfire data shows similar patterns. This is reinforced by both the spatial autocorrelation and clustering results showing some spatial change over the timeframes but almost identical patterns in the non-wildfire data. Overall, this study can confirm that VGI data changes both temporally and spatially, but wildfires do not seem to directly impact these changes.

This study was successful in identifying the need to explore idea of looking at whether VGI data can be impacted by external situation such as natural disasters and create an open-sourced methodology that can be replicated for further investigation if desired. However, the study only included two VGI platforms and four case studies across the state of California. Potential patterns could be identified in a larger study. Further analysis, such as exploring the impact of different natural hazards, or including a larger range of VGI platforms, might be considered in future work.

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Biographies

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